

AI4

Final report of Quality Assurance and data FAIRness

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1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable describes the final status of the WP7 activities since the second deliverable D7.2 [\[D7.2\]](#).

Note that the guidelines and procedures of the Software and Services Quality Assurance, have not changed with respect to the 1st release.

The work performed within the WP7 with respect to the period described in this Deliverable, has been the coordination concerning the following points:

- The 2nd software (SW) release and related components.
- The status of the FAIR assessment of the datasets.
- The infrastructure deployment, integration and operation of the AI4EOSC platform and services.

These items have been updated as necessary in the live documents in Confluence Wiki pages.

The document is structured as follows:

- [Section 2](#) describes 2nd SW release and the SQA of the several components.
- [Section 3](#) describes the status of FAIR assessment of the datasets.
- [Section 4](#) describes the distributed deployment of the several services composing the AI4EOSC platform infrastructure.
- [Section 5](#) draws final remarks.

2. SECOND SOFTWARE RELEASE

The SW release of the AI4OS stack is a point in time release. This means that SW components are continuously developed and released following a DevOps approach with CI/CD Jenkins pipelines and Github actions (cf. Deliverable [\[D7.1\]](#)). As such, the latest version of a given SW component at the time of the planned AI4OS stack release, is the one to be part of it. The 2nd release date was June 2025.

The following table shows all components together with (i) the source code repository, (ii) latest version (part of the 2nd release), (iii) the version deployed at service endpoint as part of the platform and the SQA for that version. The description of the final implementation and features for the 2nd release for the WP4 components can be found in Deliverable [\[D4.5\]](#) and for WP5 components in [\[D5.5\]](#).

Regarding the INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator, this is a platform composed of a set of other services, the details of all components is given in Deliverable [\[D4.4\]](#).

The PaaS Orchestrator is using, as a component to submit the deployment over the federated resource providers, the Infrastructure Manager.

Table 1: List of WP4 components.

SW Component (WP4)	Repository / Version / DeployedVersion (Endpoint) / SQA
PaaS Orchestrator	https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/orchestrator
	Version: 4.2.1
	DeployedVersion: 4.2.1 (https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it)
	Tests: https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/orchestrator/deployments
PaaS Dashboard	https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/orchestrator-dashboard
	Version: 4.5.1
	DeployedVersion: 4.5.1 (https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it)
Federation Registry	https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/federation-registry
	Version: 1.2.1
	DeployedVersion: 1.2.1 (https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it)
	Test: https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/federation-registry/actions
Federation Registry Feeder	https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/federation-registry-feeder
	Version: 1.3.1
	DeployedVersion: 1.3.1 (https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it)
	Test: https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/federation-registry-feeder/actions
AI-Ranker	https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/ai-ranker
	Version: 1.0.0
	DeployedVersion: 1.0.0 (https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it)
	Test: https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/ai-ranker/actions
Infrastructure Manager	https://github.com/grycap/im
	Version: 1.19.0
	DeployedVersion: 1.19.0 (https://im.egi.eu)
	EOSC-Synergy Gold: https://eu.badgr.com/public/assertions/rkXyQH9FRj-EAMPgccz5ug
Workload Management System	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-ansible - Set of Ansible recipes to deploy a combination of Nomad and Consul infrastructures, with Traefik.
	Version: 1.0.0

SW Component (WP4)	Repository / Version / DeployedVersion (Endpoint) / SQA
	DeployedVersion: 1.0.0
	Molecule tests: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-ansible/actions/workflows/main.yaml
Inference Platform	https://github.com/grycap/oscar
	Version: 3.6.3
	DeployedVersion: 3.6.3 (https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/)
	Tests: https://github.com/grycap/oscar/actions/runs/16802017992 Build: https://github.com/grycap/oscar/actions/runs/16802017972 EOSC.Synergy Silver: https://eu.badgr.com/public/assertions/0vLIQBANQzyHM0rmcsck3w

Regarding the SQA of WP4 SW components, two have earned EOSC-Synergy badges, one Gold and one Silver, while one component is actually a set of ansible roles and playbooks to deploy Nomad/Consul cluster infrastructure, it uses the Ansible Molecule test framework, the Orchestrator services have CI/CD pipelines executed through github actions.

Table 2: List of WP5 components.

SW Component (WP5)	Repository / Version / DeployedVersion (Endpoint) / SQA
Platform API	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-papi
	Version: 1.3.0
	DeployedVersion: 1.3.0 (https://api.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/)
	Precommit: https://results.pre-commit.ci/repo/github/593585153 Build image: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-papi/actions/workflows/build-docker-prod.yml Release Please: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-papi/actions/workflows/release-please.yml SonarQube: https://sonarcloud.io/component_measures?id=ai4os_ai4-papi&branch=master
Platform Dashboard	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-dashboard
	Version: 3.10.0
	DeployedVersion: 3.10.0 (https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/)
	Build image: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-dashboard/actions/workflows/build-ai4eosc-prod-dash-board.yml

SW Component (WP5)	Repository / Version / DeployedVersion (Endpoint) / SQA
	CI: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-dashboard/actions/workflows/ci-ai4eosc-dashboard.yml Release Please: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-dashboard/actions/workflows/release-please.yml Check the validity of the documentation links: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-dashboard/actions/workflows/check-links-ai4eosc-dashboard.yml SonarQube: https://codequality.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Provenance Manager	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-prov-viz/ https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-prov-api
	Version: 1.0.0
	DeployedVersion: 1.0.0 (https://provenance.services.ai4os.eu/)
	Build image: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-prov-viz/actions/workflows/main.yml Build image: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-prov-api/actions/workflows/main.yml
AI4Compose	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-compose
	Version: 2.0.0
	DeployedVersion: 1.12.2 (https://forge.flows.dev.ai4eosc.eu)
	EOSC-Synergy Silver: https://eu.badgr.com/public/assertions/mmlz4p1eTvi5-ZEwXSpUdA
Experiment tracking and Model Registry	https://github.com/m-team-kit/mlflow-auth-gui
	Version: 1.0.0
	DeployedVersion: 1.0.0 (https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/)
	EOSC-Synergy Silver: https://eu.badgr.com/public/assertions/_am9qRYnSGCcG-MzsW6UdQ
Drift monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://github.com/m-team-kit/drift-watch <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ https://github.com/m-team-kit/drift-watch-backend ◦ https://github.com/m-team-kit/drift-watch-gui-react ◦ https://github.com/m-team-kit/drift-watch-client • https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/frouros
	Version: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Backend: 1.0.0 • GUI react: 1.0.0 • Client: 1.1.0 • Frouros: 0.9.0
	DeployedVersion: 1.0.0 (https://drift-watch.cloud.ai4eosc.eu)
	Frouros: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://app.codecov.io/gh/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/frouros

SW Component (WP5)	Repository / Version / DeployedVersion (Endpoint) / SQA
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/frouros/actions/runs/16931044191/job/47976411836
Metadata manager	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-metadata
	Version: 2.4.1
	DeployedVersion: N.A.
	CI tests via tox: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-metadata/actions/workflows/ci.yml Release please: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-metadata/actions/workflows/release-please.yml Publish to PyPi: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-metadata/actions/workflows/publish-release.yml

Regarding the SQA of WP5 SW components, 2 have EOSC-Synergy Silver badges, 2 are using the SonarCube test framework through Github Actions, and the others are using a mix of tests and automated image build through Github Actions.

3. FAIR ASSESSMENT

Over the past few years, various support tools have emerged to assess the level of FAIRness of digital objects. Within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) framework, evaluating the alignment of data and services with the FAIR principles has become a strategic priority to ensure the quality, interoperability, and reusability of scientific resources. The EOSC Association coordinates several initiatives to harmonize metrics, methodologies, and FAIR assessment tools, with particular emphasis on the work of the FAIR Metrics and Data Quality Task Force². This group drives the definition of common indicators, implementation guidelines, and recommendations for adopting international standards such as the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model [RDA_FAIR]. These activities are aimed to enable consistent evaluations across infrastructures and domains as well as to integrate them into the workflows of EOSC's data repositories and catalogues, fostering a more transparent, reliable ecosystem focused on the effective reuse of research outputs.

One of the tools developed within the EOSC context is FAIR EVA³ (Evaluator, Validator and Advisor), designed to systematically assess the degree of alignment of data (or digital objects in general) and metadata with the FAIR principles. Its methodology is based on the indicators developed by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group, providing both quantitative and qualitative evaluations for each principle. Moreover, it offers actionable guidance for data producers on how to improve specific aspects to raise their FAIRness level.

² <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/fair-metrics-and-data-quality/>

³ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02652-8>

FAIR EVA allows configuring which data and metadata fields are evaluated, enabling adaptation to different contexts and communities. This flexibility makes it possible, for example, to perform quick diagnostics focused on a subset of criteria or to conduct exhaustive assessments covering all FAIR indicators. Another key feature is its plugin-based architecture, which facilitates the development of specific connectors to access data and metadata from different repositories, catalogues, or platforms. Each plugin can implement the necessary logic to locate, interpret, and normalize relevant information, thereby optimizing evaluation for each specific data source.

The digital objects of AI4EOSC can be found mainly in two environments.

- **The multidisciplinary European repository Zenodo**, used to deposit both general project documentation and the datasets employed for model training. Notably, Zenodo provides functionality for directly importing data into the AI4EOSC computational and storage environment.
- **The AI4EOSC platform's marketplace**, used to store the generated models, including metadata detailing various characteristics.

In addition, the provenance system developed within the project enriches the contextual information of the models, thereby increasing their FAIRness—particularly their interoperability and reusability.

Considering these two approaches to depositing digital objects, two FAIR EVA plugins have been employed. Zenodo offers a Signposting endpoint compatible with FAIR EVA's plugin. For connecting to and collecting data from the models, a specific plugin "ai4os"⁴ has been developed. This plugin interfaces with the metadata and provenance system to retrieve all the necessary information for the assessment.

The following subsections provide examples of different digital objects in both Zenodo and the market place, with specific evaluations. They analyse the best practices adopted within AI4EOSC as well as the limitations and potential work to improve the FAIRness of the developed resources.

3.1 - AI4EOSC CATALOG FAIRNESS

To evaluate how the AI4EOSC catalog exposes the data (modules) and metadata, the "Thermal Bridges on Building Rooftops Detection (TBBRDet)"⁵ Use Case has been selected among the others made available. It includes extensive metadata as well as information within the provenance system, which make it complete enough to be assessed with FAIR EVA. [Figure 1](#) shows the results obtained by the assessment process that are also described and explained in the following paragraphs.

⁴ Plugin available at: https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/FAIR_eva

⁵ <https://github.com/ai4os-hub/thermal-bridges-rooftops-detector>

Figure 1 - Visual results of FAIR EVA for "Thermal Bridges on Building Rooftops Detection (TBBRDet)".

FINDABILITY

For the group of indicators on findability, the score is low at 42.86%. This is because, although identifiers are used for the different modules—since it is essential that each module repository has a different name—the type of identifier used is neither persistent nor universal.

On the other hand, the metadata is indexed in the AI4EOSC platform portal itself, allowing searching and filtering according to different metadata fields.

Some improvements could be implemented to increase the findability of the modules. First, the persistent identification issues could be solved simply by assigning a Persistent Identifier (PID), such as a DOI or Handle, to each module, making it easily citable. However, at the EOSC level, there is currently no official system for assigning Persistent Identifiers. Projects such as EOSC-Beyond are working on developing a system capable of assigning identifiers to different types of components, which could be used to identify AI4EOSC modules. As a future work, whenever this system will be ready, components would be properly identified and indexing could be enhanced by linking to external initiatives or aggregators such as OpenAIRE.

ACCESSIBILITY

This group of indicators scores high at 90.7%, thanks to the detailed information and diversity in access methods. Access is provided through open, free-of-charge protocols, allowing the module's content to be retrieved via a GitHub repository and even through a Docker image hosted on DockerHub. Moreover, thanks to the provenance system, the information and metadata are exposed in semantic formats such as JSON-LD⁶, which facilitates machine interpretation. However, due to the nature of the platform, it cannot be guaranteed that the metadata will remain available if the data are not. A notable good practice is the extensive and specific documentation on access.

Although the score leaves little room for improvement, accessibility could be further enhanced by providing interfaces more typical of repository environments, such as OAI-PMH⁷ or a standard FAIR API like Signposting⁸. Another possibility would be to aggregate content into a general-purpose repository to preserve metadata even if the data (models) are temporarily unavailable.

INTEROPERABILITY

The interoperability indicators return a score of 35.48%. Despite being quite low, it is worth noting that this group of indicators is heavily oriented towards data-specific cases, as the original RDA indicators did not account for other types of resources. In the specific case of Artificial Intelligence models, there is currently no clear interoperability standard, although work is underway in this area. This is the main reason for the low score in this group.

Despite these challenges, AI4EOSC has worked on improving the interoperability of its metadata. Through a pilot usecase developed with the SEMIC Support Centre⁹, the Platform API allows the retrieval of the metadata in different ML-relevant metadata formats (like JSON-LD¹⁰ and RD Turtle¹¹), using the MLDCAT-AP profile¹². The conversion is handled by the AI4EOSC metadata tool¹³. In addition to the metadata, the platform generates RDF provenance information files about the whole pipeline that led to the model creation (e.g. training, build). This provenance system is based on W3C PROV-O¹⁴ to ensure interoperability. Throughout the project, participation in various activities and working groups aimed at improving machine learning model interoperability has taken place, such as the RDA FAIR4ML WG¹⁵. However, since no clear and universal standard has yet been established, it has not been implemented in the platform. Potential improvements to increase model interoperability include using

⁶ <https://json-ld.org/>

⁷ <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

⁸ <https://signposting.org/>

⁹ <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/semic-support-centre>

¹⁰ <https://json-ld.org/>

¹¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/turtle/>

¹² <https://semiceu.github.io/MLDCAT-AP/releases/2.0.0/>

¹³ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-metadata/>

¹⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o>

¹⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/sites/default/files/FAIR4ML-RDA-IG-Charter-v2.pdf>

controlled vocabularies (e.g., ORCID¹⁶, SPDX¹⁷) and qualified references between artefacts (dataset - model - code - container) with PIDs (linked to the findability group). Among the potential standards to enhance interoperability, two have been identified for development in future versions: Croissant, from MLCommons, which is supported by several tools and based on schema.org but is currently considered limited for AI4EOSC; and RO-Crate¹⁸ which uses DCAT¹⁹ to package artefacts and relationships, employing PIDs as qualified references. Its use is expanding across various domains and could potentially be integrated with the use of persistent identifiers within the platform.

REUSABILITY

For the last group, reusability, the score is 91.18%. Thanks to rich metadata, thorough documentation, a clearly defined license, and especially the provenance system, reusability is facilitated for other users.

A possible improvement would be to include, in addition to the license name, a clear link to the license definition in a machine-actionable format, such as those provided by SPDX.

3.2 - DIGITAL OBJECTS: DATA AND SOFTWARE AT ZENODO

To evaluate how Zenodo exposes the data and metadata of AI4EOSC datasets through the Signposting protocol, the Thermal Anomaly Segmentation Dataset²⁰ has been selected. The chosen dataset is deposited in Zenodo and enriched with the standard metadata provided by the repository. The Signposting plugin in FAIR EVA was used to automatically gather both metadata and links to related resources. [Figure 2](#) shows the results obtained by the assessment process. The final result is an 86.87% of FAIRness, higher than the modules. This is due to the fact that Zenodo is a mature multidisciplinary repository and it is oriented to provide FAIR digital objects.

¹⁶ <https://orcid.org/>

¹⁷ <https://spdx.org/rdf/spdx-terms-v1.2/terms.html>

¹⁸ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

¹⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

²⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/14287864>

Evaluation for <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14287863>

Figure 2 - Visual results of FAIR EVA for Thermal Anomaly Segmentation Dataset of AI4EOSC.

FINDABILITY

The findability score is 95.50%, which is high thanks to the presence of a persistent identifier in the form of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) provided by Zenodo and the indexing of the dataset in the repository's search interface, as well as in OpenAire. Metadata fields like title, description, creators, and keywords are all present, enhancing discoverability. However, certain qualified references and richer domain-specific keywords are missing, which could further increase the score. Improvements could include the use of additional subject classifications from controlled vocabularies (e.g., relevant disciplinary thesauri) and cross-linking to related datasets or publications through persistent identifiers.

ACCESSIBILITY

This group achieves a very high score of 87.15%, largely due to Zenodo's compliance with open and standardized protocols (HTTP(S), OAI-PMH, Signposting) and the fact that both data and metadata are open and universally accessible. The Signposting protocol further enhances machine accessibility by providing typed links to related resources. Nonetheless, there is no explicit guarantee that the metadata will remain available if the dataset itself is removed, although Zenodo is a trustworthy repository that can partially ensure sustainability. Accessibility could be improved by ensuring metadata persistence policies are explicitly stated and by offering additional standard

repository interfaces such as OAI-PMH for metadata harvesting in parallel to Signposting.

INTEROPERABILITY

The interoperability score is 85.29%, reflecting the use of standard metadata schemas (DataCite²¹ in Zenodo) and typed links from Signposting that facilitate automated navigation between resources. Some interoperability gaps are due to limited use of controlled vocabularies and the lack of qualified references between related research artefacts beyond what Signposting provides. Improvements could involve linking other controlled vocabularies, rather than creators to ORCID identifiers or licenses to SPDX URLs. Linking datasets to related code or container images with persistent identifiers, would enrich semantic relationships. In any case, those features rely on the repository capacity, which is out of the scope of the AI4EOSC project.

REUSABILITY

The reusability score is 86.87%, supported by the presence of a clear reuse license, detailed metadata, and persistent identifiers. Zenodo's integration of license information and metadata from DataCite contributes positively. However, the license reference is not always in a fully machine-actionable form (e.g., a direct SPDX URL), and some documentation aspects could be expanded to better support reuse. As an example, provenance-related information or metadata will contribute to enhancing the reusability. More features like providing a license link in a machine-readable format and extending the metadata with links to related publications, software, or datasets would support reuse in different contexts. In this case, Zenodo should include those features to enhance its functionality.

4. INFRASTRUCTURE: RESOURCES AND SERVICES FOR THE AI4EOSC PLATFORM

The AI4EOSC platform is hosted in an infrastructure that is distributed. Most of the services are deployed in cloud resources from the project partners, but there are as well, services which use external resources. The details of all services regarding their name, description, features, source code repository and license can be found in Deliverable [\[D3.4\]](#). This deliverable follows the same structure and naming.

The platform services can be divided into the following major categories:

- **Cross-platform services:** these are services not developed by the project, may be hosted by the project's cloud resource providers or external providers.
- **WP-specific project services:** these are services developed by the project, in particular by WP4, WP5 and WP6, and are hosted by the project's cloud resource providers.

²¹ <https://datacite.org/>

In the next section AI4EOSC platform services are listed with the **name**, **endpoint** (where applicable) and related **host site**.

4.1 - CROSS-PLATFORM SERVICES

GITHUB ORGANIZATIONS

There are three Github organizations used by the project:

- **AI4EOSC**: This is the main organization for all project related assets.
- **AI4OS**: This is the organization that contains the software stack that is powering the AI4EOSC platform or the iMagine platform among others.
- **AI4OS-Hub**: This is the organization that contains the main modules and tools contributed to the platforms: <https://github.com/ai4os-hub>.

Github is used for several activities:

- Source code repositories (AI4OS organization), see Section 2:
 - In several cases CI/CD pipelines through Github actions²².
- Documentation (AI4OS organization), see [Figure 3](#) for details:
 - <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/>
- Service monitoring: Upptime²³ (AI4EOSC organization):
 - <https://github.com/AI4EOSC/status>.
- AI4EOSC Architecture C4 model (AI4EOSC organization):
 - <https://github.com/AI4EOSC/ai4-architecture>.
- AI4OS Tools catalog (AI4OS organization):
 - <https://github.com/ai4os/tools-catalog>
- AI4OS Hub Modules Template (AI4OS organization):
 - <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-template>.

²² <https://github.com/features/actions>

²³ <https://github.com/upptime/upptime>

Figure 3 - AI4OS/AI4EOSC documentation.

AUTHENTICATION

The authentication system for the AI4EOSC Platform changed from the EGI Checkin to the “**AI4OS Authentication**”. This allows better control and autonomy within the project about user registration and permissions.

Name	AI4OS Authentication
Endpoints	https://login.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Host site	IFCA-LCG2 site at CSIC/IFCA

The Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure service for the PaaS components layer is provided by the INDIGO Identity and Access Management Service (**INDIGO-IAM**²⁴) that leverages the OpenID Connect (OIDC²⁵) and OAuth2.0²⁶ protocols.

Name	INDIGO IAM
Endpoints	https://aai.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/login
Host site	INFN, CSIC/IFCA

The screenshot shows the login interface for ai4eosc. At the top, the AI4 | eosc logo is displayed. Below it, the text 'Welcome to ai4eosc' is centered. A prompt 'Sign in with your ai4eosc credentials' is followed by two input fields: 'Username' (with a person icon) and 'Password' (with a lock icon). A blue 'Sign in' button is positioned below these fields. A link 'Forgot your password?' is located under the button. Below this, the text 'Or sign in with' is followed by a button containing the EGI logo. At the bottom, the text 'Not a member?' is followed by a green button labeled 'Apply for an account'.

²⁴ INDIGO-IAM service, <https://github.com/indigo-iam/iam>.

²⁵ OpenID Connect, <https://openid.net/developers/how-connect-works/>.

²⁶ OAuth 2.0, <https://oauth.net/2/>.

SECRETS MANAGER

The AI4OS Secrets manager is used to manage user sensitive data across the platform.

Name	AI4OS Secrets manager
Endpoints	https://secrets.services.ai4os.eu:8200/
Host site	IISAS-FedCloud site at IISAS

CONTAINER REGISTRY

AI4OS container registry is used as artifact repository, that is as docker container image registry

Name	AI4OS container registry
Endpoints	https://registry.services.ai4os.eu/
Host site	NCG-INGRID-PT at LIP/INCD

STORAGE

The AI4OS storage is used to store all the user related data.

Name	AI4OS Storage
Endpoints	https://share.services.ai4os.eu/
Host site	IFCA-LCG2 site at CSIC/IFCA

STATUS

AI4OS Status monitoring of all service endpoints

Name	AI4OS Status monitoring
Endpoints	https://status.ai4eosc.eu/
Host site	Github

AI4
eosc

AI4EOSC service and platform status Status GitHub

AI platform for the European Open Science Cloud.

This page provides a real time overview of the [AI4EOSC](#) platform and services status.

All systems are operational

Live Status 24h **7d** 30d 1y all

AI4 eosc **Homepage**
Overall uptime: 100.00%
Average response time: 960 ms

AI4 eosc **Dashboard (AI4EOSC)**
Overall uptime: 100.00%
Average response time: 980 ms

DYNAMIC DNS

Name	Dynamic DNS
Endpoints	https://nsupdate.fedcloud.eu/
Host site	IISAS-FedCloud site at IISAS

The screenshot shows the website for nsupdate.fedcloud.eu. The header includes the EGI logo and the Institute of Informatics, Slovak Academy of Sciences. The navigation bar contains links for Home, About, and Documentation, along with a language selector (en) and a Log in button. The main content area displays the text "Your current IP(s) + reverse DNS:" followed by the IPv4 address "IPv4: 147.213.65.150" in large blue font. Below this, the website name "nsupdate.fedcloud.eu" and its tagline "the Dynamic DNS service for EGI Federated cloud" are shown.

4.2 - WP4 SERVICES

ORCHESTRATION

The INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator middleware allows federating heterogeneous resource providers and orchestrates the deployment of TOSCA templates. The access to the PaaS Orchestrator services is provided to the final user via the PaaS Orchestrator Dashboard.

Name	PaaS Orchestrator middleware
Endpoints	https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it
Host site	INFN-CLOUD-CNAF at INFN CNAF

The screenshot shows the login page for the PaaS Orchestrator Dashboard. It features the AI4 | eosc logo on the left and the text "PaaS Orchestrator Dashboard" on the right. A blue button labeled "Login with IAM »" is positioned at the bottom center.

INFRASTRUCTURE MANAGER

The Infrastructure Manager is an IaaS tool designed to manage the creation of virtual infrastructures and platforms.

Name	Infrastructure Manager
Endpoints	https://im.egi.eu
Host site	GRyCAP - UPV

The screenshot shows the 'IM Dashboard' with a navigation bar for 'Infrastructures', 'Advanced', and 'External Links'. A search bar is present. Below are six deployment cards: 'Deploy a VM' (with a VM icon), 'Deploy an OSCAR Virtual Cluster' (with OSCAR logo), 'Deploy a Kubernetes Virtual Cluster' (with Kubernetes logo), 'SLURM virtual cluster' (with SLURM logo), 'Deploy Kubeflow on top of a Kubernetes Virtual Cluster' (with Kubeflow logo), and 'TOSCA Template' (with TOSCA logo).

WORKLOAD MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Federated Workload Management System (Federated WMS) enables orchestrated workload execution across multiple datacenters

Name	Federated WMS
Endpoints	Consul dashboard: http://193.146.75.205:8500/ Nomad dashboard: https://193.146.75.205:4646/
Host site	IFCA-LCG2 site at CSIC/IFCA

INFERENCE PLATFORM

A platform based on OSCAR (Open-source Serverless Computing for Data-Processing Applications) for serverless event-driven data-processing applications.

Name	AI as a Service
Endpoints	https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Host site	NCG-INGRID-PT at LIP/INCD

Name	Image	CPU	Memory
cowsay	ghcr.io/grycap/cowsay	1.0	1Gi
plants	grycap/oscar-theano-plants	1.0	1Gi
plants-classification	ai4oshub/plants-classification	1.0	2Gi
resnet-50	ghcr.io/rk181/mlserver:resnet-50	1.0	2Gi
thermal-detector	ai4oshub/thermal-bridges-rooftops-detector	3.0	4Gi
thermal-detector-test	ai4oshub/thermal-bridges-rooftops-detector	3.0	4Gi

4.3 - WP5 SERVICES

PLATFORM API

The Platform API seamlessly orchestrates the different platform components.

Name	AI4OS Platform API
Endpoints	https://api.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Host site	IFCA-LCG2 site at CSIC/IFCA
<pre>{ "versions": [{ "version": "stable", "id": "v1", "links": [{ "rel": "self", "type": "application/json", "href": "https://api.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/v1/" }] }, { "rel": "help", "type": "text/html", "href": "https://api.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/docs" }, { "rel": "help", "type": "text/html", "href": "https://api.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/redoc" }, { "rel": "describedby", "type": "application/json", "href": "https://api.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/openapi.json" }] }</pre>	

PLATFORM DASHBOARD

The AI4EOSC platform provides an easy to use toolbox to develop artificial intelligence and machine learning models.

Name	AI4OS Platform Dashboard
Endpoints	https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Host site	IFCA-LCG2 site at CSIC/IFCA

PROVENANCE MANAGER

Provenance Manager is a tool responsible for fetching metadata from the different AI4EOsc components and building a detailed provenance graph

Name	Provenance Manager
Endpoints	https://provenance.services.ai4os.eu/
Host site	IFCA-LCG2 site at CSIC/IFCA

AI4COMPOSE

AI4Compose is a software suite designed to integrate and orchestrate various AI models and machine learning techniques into organised workflows.

Name	AI4Compose
Endpoints	https://forge.flows.dev.ai4eosc.eu
Host site	NCG-INGRID-PT at LIP/INCD

EXPERIMENT TRACKING AND MODEL REGISTRY

Name	AI4OS Experiment tracking
Endpoints	https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Host site	NCG-INGRID-PT at LIP/INCD

DRIFT MONITORING

A simple to use library to monitor drift detection jobs.

Name	AI4OS DriftWatch
Endpoints	https://drift-watch.cloud.ai4eosc.eu
Host site	KIT

METADATA MANAGER

A tool to manage common operations performed on AI4OS metadata.

Name	AI4OS Metadata manager
Endpoints	Local installation
Host site	N.A.

CI/CD

A service to orchestrate the CI/CD Pipelines of the different AI modules and tools.

Name	AI4OS CI/CD manager
Endpoints	https://jenkins.services.ai4os.eu/
Host site	IFCA-LCG2 site at CSIC/IFCA

The screenshot shows the Jenkins dashboard with a green header. On the left, there are navigation links: 'Historial de Compilações', 'Relação dos Projectos', and 'Verificar a Impressão Digital de Ficheiro'. Below these are two summary boxes: 'Fila de Compilações' (Sem builds em espera) and 'Estado de execução de builds' (Agent 01: 0/16, slava 01: 0/32). The main area displays a table of build history under the 'All' filter.

S	W	Name ↓	Último Sucesso
		AI4EOSC	1 hr 46 min log
		AI4OS	31 min log
		AI4OS Hub Building (QA)	3 hr 34 min log
		AI4OS Hub Housekeeping	21 hr log
		AI4OS Hub Testing (user jobs)	3 hr 33 min log

AI4EOSC LLM

A service to serve LLMs for users through a friendly UI.

Name	AI4OS LLM
Endpoints	https://llm.dev.ai4eosc.eu/
Host site	IFCA-LCG2 site at CSIC/IFCA

4.4 - WP6 SERVICES AND COMPONENTS

MODULES TEMPLATES

The AI4 Templates Hub allows developers and users to create software project repositories, following AI4EOsc best practices and recommendations.

Name	AI4OS Templates
Endpoints	https://templates.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Host site	IISAS-FedCloud site at IISAS

MODULE REPOSITORIES

Github organization that contains the main modules and tools contributed to the platforms.

Name	AI4OS Hub
Endpoints	https://github.com/ai4os-hub
Host site	Github

DATASETS

The project’s datasets are published in Zenodo and have a DOI to comply with FAIR principles, see [Figure 4](#):

https://zenodo.org/communities/ai4eosc/records?q=&f=resource_type%3Adataset.

The FAIR assessment with FAIR-EVA for one of the datasets was described in Section [3.2](#).

The screenshot shows the AI4EOOSC Zenodo repository interface. The header includes the AI4EOOSC logo and navigation links. The main content area displays search results for datasets, with filters on the left and a list of results on the right. The results list includes:

- Thermal Anomaly Segmentation Dataset - Thermal UAS-based Images from Germany with Annotations for Semantic Segmentation Model Training** (July 29, 2025, 0.0.1). Authors: Ruck, Julian; Vollmer, Elena; Volk, Rebekka, and 1 other. Description: The Thermal Anomaly Segmentation (TASeg) dataset is provided in accompaniment of the paper "Leak detection using thermal imagery: Deep learning versus traditional computer vision state-of-the-art" and can be utilised for the multi-stage training of spectral deep learning models for binary semantic segmentation. Specifically, this model is utilised in the context of leak detection in...
- Plant image classification dataset** (July 13, 2025, 0.1.0). Author: Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center. Description: Overview: This repository contains 1215 high-resolution RGB images captured by PSNC and WOODR for the dataset specifically designed for training two models to recognize Cercospora Leaf in beet and Brown Rust of Rye in rye. The dataset has been utilized to train CNN models for product available at AI4EOOSC marketplace that are integrated into the mobile application of eDWI...
- Thermal Urban Feature Segmentation - Multispectral (RGB + Thermal) UAS-based images from Germany with annotations** (February 27, 2025, 0.0.1). Authors: Vollmer, Elena; König, Susannah; Horstmann, Vanessa, and 4 others. Description: The Thermal Urban Feature Segmentation (TUFSeg) dataset consists of annotated and combined RGB and thermal images, acquired by uncrewed aircraft system (UAS). They show various nighttime scenes from two German cities: Munich and Karlsruhe. Owing to the high overlap of 88%, only select images were annotated to prevent duplicate instances. See the "Usage" section...
- Plant leaves image segmentation dataset** (January 20, 2025, 0.1.0). Author: PSNC. Description: Overview: This repository contains high-resolution RGB images captured by field advisors and selected by experts for the dataset specifically designed for training two models to recognize Cercospora Leaf Spot Disease in beet and Brown Rust of Rye in rye. The dataset comprises 397 images and includes original photos along with binary masks for two categories: leaf...

Figure 4 - AI4EOOSC datasets published in Zenodo.

4.5 - CLOUD INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS

The cloud compute infrastructure hosting all AI4EOOSC services, are provided by five OpenStacks sites hosted by AI4EOOSC partners:

- IFCA-LCG2 site at CSIC/IFCA: <https://portal.cloud.ifca.es/>.
- IISAS-FedCloud site at IISAS: <https://cloud.ui.savba.sk/>.
- NCG-INGRID-PT at LIP/INCD: <https://stratus.ncg.ingrid.pt/>.
- INFN-CLOUD-BARI at INFN Bari: <https://cloud.recas.ba.infn.it/>.
- INFN-CLOUD-CNAF at INFN CNAF: <https://cloud-dashboard.cnaf.infn.it/>.

All sites are integrated in the EGI Federated Cloud, thus integrated with the EGI Check-in and support "vo.ai4eosc.eu" VO. Only members of the VO "operators" group can manage the cloud resources.

5. FINAL REMARKS

This document describes the final status of all activities of WP7.

The second release, and related components, were described in [Section 2](#), where we give the list of all SW components from WP4 and WP5 that compose the first AI4OS stack together with the SQA on those components. Some are using the SQAaaS from EOSC Synergy and others are using specific CI/CD pipelines executed in the project's Jenkins server through Github actions.

The FAIR assessment status is described in [Section 3](#). In the framework of AI4EOSC, two FAIR assessments with the FAIR-EVA tool have been described, one for a module and another for a dataset, and the results presented.

The Software components developed within the project are deployed in the federated cloud infrastructure that can be accessed by the users, and for execution of the use case applications. All the mentioned components are in production and have been deployed into the Platform.

REFERENCES

- [D7.1]** Mario David. (2023). D7.1 - Initial plan for Quality Assurance and data FAIRness. Zenodo, Mar 14, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7732923>.
- [D3.3]** Calatrava, A., López García, A., & Berberi, L. (2024). D3.3 - Final high-level architecture specification. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11485109>
- [D4.3]** Costantini, A., Sáinz-Pardo, J., Kozlov, V., Dlugolinsky, S., Alarcón, C., & Moltó, G. (2024). D4.3 - WP4 Updated implementation plan and progress report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11485120>
- [D5.3]** Heredia, I. (2024). D5.3 - WP5 Updated implementation plan and progress report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11485132>
- [D7.2]** David, M., Tran, V., & Aguilar, F. (2024). AI4EOSC - D7.2 - Status report on Quality Assurance and data FAIRness. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10869540>
- [D3.4]** Calatrava, A., Heredia, I., & Molto, G. , AI4EOSC - D3.4- AI4EOSC Catalogue of Services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16737905>
- [D4.4]** Costantini, A., Caballer, M., Heredia, I., Calatrava, A., Moltó, G., Fernandez Tobias, S., Sainz-Pardo, J. (2025). Second release of the AI Platform as a Service. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10.5281/zenodo.16737927>
- [D4.5]** Costantini, A., Caballer, M., Heredia, I., Calatrava, A., Moltó, G., Fernandez Tobias, S., Sainz-Pardo, J. (2025). WP4 Final implementation report <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16737936>
- [D5.4]** Heredia, I., Obregón, M., Calatrava, A., Moltó, G., Berberi, L., Esteban Sanchis, B., Diez, J., Castro, P., Dlugolinsky, S., Sainz-Pardo, J. (2025). Second release of experiment centric and composite-AI tools <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16737943>
- [D5.5]** Heredia, I., Obregón, M., Calatrava, A., Moltó, G., Berberi, L., Esteban Sanchis, B., Diez, J., Castro, P., Dlugolinsky, S., Sainz-Pardo, J. (2025). WP5 Final implementation report <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16737951>
- [RDA_FAIR]** FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CLI	Command Line Interface
DO	Digital Object
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
IM	Infrastructure Manager
OWASP	Open Web Application Security Project
OSS	Open Source Software
PR	Pull Request
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SAST	Static Application Security Testing
SCM	Software Configuration Management
SQA	Software Quality Assurance
SvcQA	Service Quality Assurance
SQAaaS	Software Quality Assurance as a Service
VCS	Version Control System

